

The Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin as a Participatory Space

Exploratory research and conceptualisation of new participatory offerings and
space utilisation scenarios using the example of the Stabi Lab

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1. Introduction

Academic and state libraries are increasingly confronted with a dual expectation. On one hand, an expectation to act as infrastructures for digital research and scholarship; on the other, a demand for openness, low-threshold offerings and public engagement beyond their more traditional academic public. Rather than being opposed in principle, these expectations often generate tensions in practice, for example in terms of resources, staffing and design or prioritising of formats.

These challenges and this redefinition of the traditional missions and self-perception of academic libraries have led many institutions to experiment with new formats, such as labs or makerspaces. However, little research has been done to date on hybrid labs that promote the productive and creative use of digital cultural heritage data in physical spaces or on the role of library labs without clearly defined target groups.

This study aims to address this gap through an explorative and empirical approach. It explores how hybrid labs in physical library spaces can encourage participatory, inclusive and creative engagement with digital cultural heritage data and serve as spaces of exchange and collaboration for diverse communities, and draws on the analysis of a series of pilot formats organised and conducted by the Stabi Lab at the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin. These included, for example, Citizen Science workshops, hackathons and coworking scenarios. These formats functioned as both public-facing activities and materials for the lab's self-reflection and for the study, by producing user-generated content, qualitative and quantitative feedback data or simply documentation.

It combines this analysis of situated practices within the Stabi Lab with theoretical perspectives from library and information science and digital humanities, grounding the case study in broader scholarly discourses. This case study of the Stabi Lab is not to be understood as an evaluation at the end of a cycle, or as a finished model, but rather as an always evolving ecosystem and through which broader questions of public engagement and participation, hybridity or staff involvement, for example, can be examined.

The overarching objective of this project was the development of a generic and transferable concept for hybrid cultural data labs in library spaces that could be adapted to a variety of institutions, with a particular relevance for academic libraries that do not have a clearly assigned target audience. Far from being prescriptive, this framework is intended to work as an analytical and self-reflective tool, that helps institutions or labs describe their existing practices, identify gaps and tensions and make informed decisions. A central challenge was to balance this need for transferability and generic applicability with the reality that each lab is nested within a unique and specific institutional context. To address this tension, I tried to focus on some recurring orientations or concepts, such as hybridity, practice and iteration, or levels of support, through which labs' practices can be analysed and compared while respecting their characteristics and situatedness.

The study begins with a conceptual foundation that grounds hybrid library labs at the intersection of digital humanities, library and information science and participatory cultures. It then introduces the framework and the process and methodology through which it emerged and developed. The following chapters focus then on the Stabi Lab as a case study and, drawing on it, discuss best practices, limitations and possible future perspectives, both for the Stabi Lab and for similar institutions.

By grounding this study in both conceptual and theoretical reflection and an empirical case study, the project aims to contribute to practical knowledge for libraries or library labs navigating the same challenges as the Staatsbibliothek, such as digital transformation or the emergence of new ways of working and learning.

This research was conducted between 2024 and 2025 as part of the exploratory project *“Die Staatsbibliothek als Mitmach-Raum. Explorative Erforschung und Konzeptualisierung neuer Partizipationsangebote und Raumnutzungsszenarien am Beispiel des Stabi Lab”* (“The State Library as a Participatory Space”), funded by the Federal Commissioner for Culture and the Media (BKM).

2. Foundations: Two Perspectives on Library Labs

Rather than providing a comprehensive literature review, this chapter engages in a focused discussion of two contributions that serve as conceptual foundations for the framework developed in this paper: Urszula Pawlicka-Deger who theorizes a “laboratory turn” in the humanities and Katy Webb who developed a “studio model”, which provides a structured way of designing and evaluating creative spaces within academic or university libraries. Their models are used here as the main theoretical anchors for the framework, which will be presented in the next chapter, and are complemented by some additional perspectives from LIS and digital humanities fields, as well as institutional strategy texts such as *Wissenschaftliche Bibliotheken 2025* and the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin strategic paper *Stabi 2030*.

My intention was not to reproduce these models directly but to understand how their approach and propositions could inform my understanding of the Stabi Lab case and, in turn, how these learnings could help shape my own model. Both Pawlicka-Deger and Webb view labs as dynamic and evolving environments and offer a framework to think about them in terms of processes or orientations rather than a rigid set of characteristics.

2.1 Digital Humanities Labs and the “Laboratory Turn” (Pawlicka-Deger)

The emergence of Digital Humanities (DH) labs in the past decades has been addressed as part of a broader transformation in the humanities field, leaning towards more collaborative and experimental forms of knowledge production. Pawlicka-Deger, for example, argues that the rise of humanities labs represents “*a laboratory turn*”,¹ where humanities moved beyond their traditional environment (e.g. the office, the seminar room, the library) into spaces shaped by experimentation and situated practices:

“The shift towards inter- and transdisciplinary practices and social engagement was accompanied by the symbolic gesture of moving the humanities “beyond the walls of the office” into the public domain. The humanities moved out of their usual spaces — the office and the library — into a new territory — the center — to intensify interdisciplinarity and public engagement.” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 3)

Taking from laboratory studies, she highlights that what makes these labs distinctive is not solely the presence of scientific equipment but the underlying ethos and shared values behind them: “The lab becomes conceptualized as a way of thinking entailing new social practices and new research modes (collaboration, experimentation, and hands-on practices). Hence, the laboratory turn has been driven by the movement away from building physical labs towards creating concept-based laboratories (lab courses, lab projects).” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 16)

In her article, Pawlicka-Deger proposes a typology of humanities labs which share certain principles but differ in purpose. She defines five distinct models, each with specific functions and situatedness:

- center-type labs often evolved from former digital humanities centres. Their main role is to advance (digital) humanities scholarship, by providing resources and supporting the use of digital methods whether for research or for teaching.
- the techno-science lab is primarily production-oriented. It focuses on the development of digital tools, platforms and research outputs and views technology as both a method and an object of inquiry.

¹ Pawlicka-Deger, Urszula. (2020). The Laboratory Turn: Exploring Discourses, Landscapes, and Models of Humanities Labs, "Digital Humanities Quarterly". 14.

- the work station-type lab operates mainly as an infrastructure provider. It aims at supplying facilities and equipment, and offering technical assistance and training to facilitate scholarly work.
- the social challenges-centric lab is driven by public engagement and aims at addressing social issues. It prioritizes community impact and participatory research.
- the virtual lab moves beyond physical space or a fixed location. It relies primarily on digital infrastructures and, while it might incorporate characteristics or functions associations with other types of labs, its main defining feature lies in its virtual situatedness.

Pawlicka-Deger also underlines that labs often mix “place” and “space”. Again, drawing on laboratory studies, she highlights that labs are conceptual and social spaces, and might not even always be situated in physical rooms or shaped by material conditions:

“The notion of the laboratory is used in terms of new modes of research and community outreach which do not necessarily require a fixed physical location and equipment. This significant change reflects the meaning of the laboratory turn: the lab does not refer to a physical place anymore; instead, it is related to a way of thinking, communicating, and working” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 4).

This perspective is particularly helpful for thinking about hybrid formats and about space/place questions that will reappear in the Stabi Lab analysis.

Finally, the laboratory turn in the humanities also has institutional roots. Early DH centres were often isolated or positioned as “peripheral enclaves” at the margins of universities and usually rather precarious. Pawlicka-Deger² sums up the situation by quoting Julie Thompson Klein,³ “*the word ‘centre’ is ironic, for many were not central to the mission of the institution*”. In this context, the rise of the lab model offered an alternative and a strategic response to the structural crisis of the centres; they were meant to encourage experimentation and collaboration instead of service-focused missions and of the siloed work that were often the reality of the centres:

“Weakening centers and redirecting digital humanities converged with the boom of laboratories in the humanities and social sciences, and also outside of the academy walls. [...] Taken together, whereas a center and department foster digital humanities as a discipline, a laboratory propagates digital humanities as a method and practice that is by nature distributed and decentralized.” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2019)

This historical context helps understand why labs are often navigating a certain ambiguity between service functions and more experimental or exploratory roles. It also explains why frameworks or conceptual models for labs must acknowledge and embrace some level of fluidity. At the same time, this emphasis on experimentation and openness also has its limits. For example, during an exchange session organised by the Stabi Lab with other labs and Digital Humanities initiatives within the Berlin landscape, a participant noted that this persistent rhetoric of fluidity and experimentation can complicate efforts to secure long-term institutional resources or recognition. This suggests that, while recognizing ambiguity may be productive in terms of practice, labs also require some form of positioning that legitimates them within institutional contexts. This tension points to the need for complementary models which can address the issue of sustainability more explicitly. Pawlicka-Deger herself identifies sustainability as a key unresolved challenge in her paper, noting that “one challenge of the humanities lab remains to be discussed: its sustainability,” meaning “maintaining the long-term

² Pawlicka-Deger, Urszula. *Laboratory: A New Space in Digital Humanities*. *Debates in the Digital Humanities: Institutions, Infrastructures at the Interstices*. University of Minnesota Press, 2019.

³ Klein, Julie Thompson. *Humanities, Culture, and Interdisciplinarity: The Changing American Academy*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 2005, p. 76.

viability of a lab and sustaining the commitments of time and effort made by the people who are the core of the laboratory” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 18).

This is where more practice-oriented frameworks can become particularly valuable and complement Pawlicka-Deger’s conceptual insights with tools that are more explicitly concerned with how library creative spaces and labs can be organised and staffed.

2.2 The Studio Model (Webb & Sesink)

While Pawlicka-Deger provides an historical account of humanities labs and how research practices in the (digital) humanities evolved, Katy Kavanagh Webb and Laurents Sesink offer a more practice-oriented framework for understanding and designing library creative spaces.

Their work focuses on how libraries can support research and creative processes through what she calls the “studio” model; she writes that “a lab as studio encourages people to take part in active experimentation and prototyping with new concepts and ideas”⁴. In this model, library creative spaces or labs can be understood as dynamic and evolving environments where users can explore and “engage in new ways of scholarship” (Webb & Sesink, 2024, p. 475).

A central element of Webb and Sesink’s approach is the proposal of a lab engagement pyramid to “distinguish models for deploying trained staff and resources within the library lab space”. This conceptual pyramid and the associated framework help guiding libraries in planning and benchmarking their services, offerings, resources and staffing models, according to their institutional goals. They identified seven types of library labs, each with their own engagement strategy, that they sum up as following:

- Lab as display for research: An open area, usually in a highly trafficked section of the library, with displays showing how to do digital scholarship or exhibiting products of digital research.
- Lab as classroom: A technology-enabled classroom with hybrid meeting technology set aside specifically for the instruction of digital scholarship methodology.
- Lab as technology depot: Multiple small rooms or one large room with specialized technology, for example, virtual reality or 3D printers.
- Lab as central location for expert help: A space that offers help from specialized staff, usually with office hours for walk-ins and a workshop series.
- Lab as researcher collective: Some libraries call their digital humanities, data, or scholars’ research group a lab but lack a physical location for their activities. A lab as researcher collective may set aside space for the group to meet or have a long-term project space.

Figure 1 “The types of library labs can be arranged on a lab engagement and skills pyramid according to what they require to operate. The arrow on the left shows the engagement and development called for, while that on the right indicates the level of skilled staff needed. A lab as studio takes the most engagement and the most staff, while a lab as display for research requires the least of both.”

(Webb & Sesink, 2024, p. 477)

⁴ Webb, Katy, and Laurents Sesink. "Engagement Scenarios for Tomorrow’s Library Labs." *portal: Libraries and the Academy* 24, no. 3 (2024): 473–86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1353/pla.2024.a931768>.

- Lab as community or thematic hub: A space where people meet to collaborate, either with an expert or in small groups via a community of practice, focused on a specific topic.
- Lab as studio: A space that encourages active experimentation, prototyping, and even failure with new concepts and ideas.

(Webb & Sesink, 2024, p. 476)

The pyramid model suggests increasing levels of engagement and resource amount, from simple display role to active experimentation and co-creation. However, rather than adopting this pyramid as a prescriptive and hierarchical model, this study uses it as a tool for reflection and diagnostic. The Stabi Lab case indeed shows that several of these types often coexist, sometimes even within the same format. In this sense, the value of Webb and Sesink's framework for this project lies less in its hierarchy, that was not translated in the framework, than in its capacity to explicit the different modes of engagement a lab can have and the implications that comes with them, in terms of resources and staffing for example.

What was also particularly useful for this project in Webb's approach is her development of tools to help library creative spaces map their current practices and that link different forms of engagement to staffing models, services offered and institutional goals. She proposes a constellation of different tools, which aim at revealing what a space currently offers[?] but also what it could offer, what Webb calls "tomorrow's engagement scenarios".

For example, one of the key components of Webb's research lies in the importance of fostering research practices. For her, library lab staff interactions with researchers can fall into three, and later four, categories: "doing it for people," "showing people how," "doing it with people", where "scholars and librarians are partners to create a project", and eventually also "community of practices". This requires the staff to be "experts who can guide, facilitate, and train the researchers" (Webb & Sesink, 2024, p. 475). This mirrors the Stabi Lab's case, where the staff might alternate between teaching, facilitation or coordination according to the event. The models therefore provide an interesting conceptual grounding to understand the diversity of Stabi Lab's formats and the different levels of support that exist within this constellation.

Finally, Webb also indicates that creative spaces must be well established within broader institutional ecosystems if they want to remain sustainable; for example, for an academic library creative space nested within a university, that would mean ensuring that that the lab "dovetails with and builds upon the mission and vision of the university" (Webb & Sesink, 2024, p. 485). A lab with strong partnerships or aligned or supported by an institutional is thus more likely to evolve and hold on over time. This emphasis responds to the limits highlighted in Pawlicka-Deger's model by addressing more practically questions of sustainability, visibility and long-term support. For this reason, this study also draws on strategy documents such as *Wissenschaftliche Bibliotheken 2025* or *Stabi 2030*, which underline the need for libraries to position themselves as "collaborative hubs" that support digital transformation and literacy.

2.3 The Lab at the Intersection of Digital Humanities, LIS and Participatory Discourses

The emergence of the modern lab as a dynamic and hybrid space is the result of overlapping discourses, coming from different fields such as the Digital Humanities, Library and Information Science (LIS) and the broader cultural movement toward participatory practice. Pawlicka-Deger notes, for example, that the development of the laboratory in the humanities was driven by the “expansion of cultural categories of innovation, the maker movement (the proliferation of makerspaces), and the idea of community”. She indicates that the concept of what a lab is has been “expanded and altered by social initiatives, such as library creative spaces, makerspaces, and hackathons” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 1).

Webb and Sesink’s article mirrors this shift in the LIS field, viewing the library as an ideal location for creative spaces that facilitate new modes of engagement.

This is reinforced by current discourses in institutional (GLAM) strategies, which see the lab as a component of their development. The *Wissenschaftliche Bibliotheken 2025* (“*Scientific Libraries 2025*”), a strategic paper from the German Library Association which outlines key areas of action for academic libraries, for example, explicitly establishes the goal of the “establishment of creative spaces (cultural labs, community-oriented makerspaces)” as a future objective for research libraries. By developing these spaces, libraries aim to respond to current challenges and actively support digital transformation. The *Stabi 2030* paper, the official strategy document of the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin that outlines its long-term vision, also aligns with this support for creative and collaborative spaces; it lists for example the goal or aspirations of being a “lively meeting place [...] promoting cultural and social diversity” and it strives to be at the “interface between research and society”. The Stabi Lab is explicitly given as an example of a cross-departmental space for experience and learning (Stabi 2030, p. 12). It situates and legitimates it as part of a larger institutional orientation towards more participation and interdisciplinary collaboration.

2.4 Towards a Framework

The models presented by Pawlicka-Deger and Webb and Sesink, though based in different disciplines, share a conceptual ground that forms the foundation of this project framework. Both authors view the lab not as a rigid entity but as a dynamic and hybrid environment, defined by a constellation of activities from “research, design, work station, service, pedagogical, and public engagement” (Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p.9) to the integration of “mindset, skill set, tool set, programs, and staffing” (Webb and Sesink, 2024, p. 275).

Moreover, both models think the lab beyond its physical location, in that they are not primarily or solely defined by dedicated spaces or technical infrastructures. Pawlicka-Deger’s “laboratory turn” highlights that the “lab” represents more of a way of thinking and working rather than a fixed physical place. Similarly, Webb and Sesink similarly conceptualise types of labs, such as the researcher collective, that can operate without a physical location. In both cases, the lab is understood as a constellation of practices, people, resources and shared ethos, and not only through its physical situatedness.

Both frameworks and institutional strategic papers also shift the emphasis from service-oriented roles towards active collaboration practices. Labs are not only providers of tools or support but truly are meant to encourage practices of collaboration, co-creation, experimentation and prototyping. Pawlicka-Deger offers us an historical and conceptual understanding of this shift and Webb and Sesink translate this into practical engagement scenarios for library creatives spaces.

These perspectives informed the development of the framework proposed in this study, which combines elements from both approaches and intentionally departed from the pyramidal logic of

Webb and Sesink or from adopting their existing typology. From Pawlicka-Deger's model, it draws more a theoretical and historical context as well as an understanding of labs being shaped as much by people, practices or values as by spaces or their technical infrastructures. Webb and Sesink's provides us with a more practice-oriented tools and insights on practices of engagement and staff role.

These elements are assembled into a modular framework which allows different orientations to coexist without a hierarchical order or a fixed or prescriptive typology. This modularity proved quite relevant in the context of the Stabi Lab, where formats and audiences tend to overlap, making rigid distinctions or a linear and pyramidal development model difficult to apply. This conceptual foundation provides the basis for the analysis of the Stabi Lab as a case study in the following chapter.

3. How a Framework Emerges: Between Theory, Benchmarking, and Practice

Building on the foundations previously developed, this chapter retraces how the framework for a hybrid library lab in this study was conceptualized using three complementary approaches. First, the theoretical perspectives discussed earlier, particularly Pawlicka-Deger's "laboratory turn" and Webb and Sesink's studio model, as well as other more hands-on resources such as *Open a GLAM Lab*, provided an initial vocabulary and tools to think labs through. Then, a comparative analysis of existing GLAM or library labs allowed me to observe how these concepts materialise in different examples and institutional contexts. Finally, I conducted an internal analysis of the Stabi Lab, using available data such as user studies, event documentation and statistics, the internal concept paper of the Stabi Lab and institutional strategy documents such as *Stabi 2030*, which was already mentioned in Chapter 2.

This approach made it possible to connect conceptual insights and more empirical evidence or observations, in order to design a framework that is both theoretically grounded and practically informed. This framework thus emerged gradually, through an iterative back-and-forth between strands of literature and concrete experience coming from the Stabi Lab. The goal was not only to describe what exists, nor to simply prescribe what a lab "should" be or "should" do, but to construct a flexible tool for reflection that is adaptable to different institutional contexts.

3.1. Defining "Labness": What Makes a Lab a Lab?

When I first started to map existing GLAM Labs, I very soon realised how difficult it was to define what a "lab" actually is. The term is used across a wide constellation of spaces (whether digital or physical), initiatives and programmes which differ especially in activities institutional setting or resources. Some are structured research environments with a permanent staff and budgets, others are project-based or temporary experimentations.

This diversity of forms makes it almost impossible to capture what a lab is through a single definition. Thus, this study adopts the concept of "labness" as an analytical lens, practically a state that can be expressed in different forms and degrees, through which lab initiatives can be analysed, based on what they do or enable. Drawing on the benchmarking of several existing international labs as well as on the literature discussed in Chapter 2, several common principles and recurring activities or patterns of "labness" became visible.

Many labs articulate similar orientations, for example openness, experimentation, creativity, participation or inclusivity. These principles are often reflected in their mission statements or mottos, or directly embedded in their events and formats programming strategy.

In terms of practices or functional components, labs tend to combine different elements, such as physical spaces and infrastructures, digital tools and platforms and community outreach.

These patterns resonate with Pawlicka-Deger's definition of the humanities lab as both an infrastructure and a set of practices and activities.

"A laboratory in the humanities is a technical, research, and intellectual infrastructure for humanistic issues and inquiries which offers space (physical, virtual or conceptual), community, and resources to conduct a set of activities resulting from its specific function (e.g. research, design, work station, service, pedagogical, and public engagement). Laboratory initiatives are guided by the following principles: interdisciplinarity, collaboration, co-creation, team-based, and experimentation."

(Pawlicka-Deger, 2020, p. 9)

These recurring patterns of “labness” also closely mirror how the Stabi Lab is conceptualised internally. In its internal concept paper⁵, the lab is framed as an infrastructure combining curated data offers available online (DataLab), a physical environment for experimentation and for exchange (LabSpace), and a programme of diverse events and formats. This structure reflects the understanding of a lab as both infrastructure and practice.

This comparative perspective helped to situate the Stabi Lab within a broader ecosystem and also to identify potential gaps or areas where it could offer something distinctive, for example through its focus on hybrid participation models in the context of a state or regional library - as opposed to libraries with a clear target group, such as university libraries.

3.2. Empirical Grounding: Studying the Stabi Lab

Beyond theory and benchmarking, the framework emerged from observing and analysing the Stabi Lab itself. It was meant to be abstract enough to be transferable, but also concrete in a way that reflects the Staatsbibliothek’s specific dynamics, the lab being not only an example for the framework, but a place of co-creation where empirical observation and conceptual modelling would inform each other.

Data sources included a 2018 user profile survey⁶ (the most comprehensive quantitative overview of the Staatsbibliothek’s users to date) and internal event documentation and evaluation since the creation of the lab in 2019.

Although the 2018 survey does not show us the possible transformations in library use after COVID-19, it still reveals valuable tendencies; besides, its limitations might be balanced by the more recent event evaluations and observations that were also used. Together, these materials made it possible to analyse user needs, participation patterns and strategic orientations.

The user survey shows that the Stabi’s audience is quite diverse: 25% students, 18% doctoral researchers, 22% independent researchers, and 33% scientifically interested citizens. Two-thirds belong to the humanities, and most users describe themselves as individual learners (70%). While 80% are aware of workshops and events, fewer than 10% participate. Half of the respondents value personal advice and support from staff.

This indicates a strong interest in self-paced learning, but also a need for spaces of informal exchange and support. These insights informed not only the Stabi lab’s programming, but also the conceptual structure of the framework itself.

⁵ Stabi Lab. Ausbau des Stabi Labs zu einem zentralen Hub digitaler Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften an der Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin

⁶ Berthold, Judith. Nutzergruppen und ihre Motive für die Benutzung der Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin und ihrer Dienstleistungen: eine quantitative Umfrage. Berlin: Institut für Bibliotheks- und Informationswissenschaft der Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, 2018.

3.3. From Data to Framework

- **The Four Core Modules**

The framework emerged through synthesis: by combining the conceptual perspectives discussed in Chapter 2, observations from the benchmarking of other GLAM and library labs, and the Stabi Lab's own data and material. From this process, four recurrent orientations became visible, later structured as the framework's core modules: Community Builder, Research Accelerator, Creative Innovation Hub, and Tech & Tools Depot.

Each module corresponds to a cluster of activities and values observed either in the Stabi Lab or in international examples. They can serve as a way to map, analyse, and plan; they help categorize existing activities and also make visible where gaps, overlaps, or tensions occur.

- **Community Builder**

The Community Builder module emphasizes participation, inclusion and exchange, over expertise for example. These labs focus on creating spaces where diverse publics can engage with each other and with cultural data and library collections. Typical activities include storytelling formats, crowdsourcing initiatives, participatory transcription or annotation projects.

The added value of this module lies in lowering barriers to participation. Within the Stabi Lab, formats such as Coding Gender (2020), the ongoing Datencafé or the culture.explore(data) Hackathon (2025) exemplify this module, as they lean into public engagement and collaborative work on cultural data. Within the logic of Stabi 2030, this orientation resonates strongly with goals from the strategic paper, in which the library acts a space for social discourse and a civic meeting place.

This Community Builder module draws on Pawlicka-Deger's notion of public-facing labs as well as on Webb and Sesink's community or thematic hubs. It also reflects a broader discourse around public participation within the GLAM field.

- **Research Accelerator**

The Research Accelerator module focuses on collaborative and experimental research practices using cultural data. Labs in this orientation aim at supporting researchers, students or research software engineers (RSE) in working with library collections in a more expert way. Examples of activities and events would be data sprints, peer exchange formats or research residencies.

Here, the lab's added value lies in fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and exchange among expert users. In the Stabi Lab context, events such as *Faithful Transcriptions* (2021) or the *Blauer Salon* (ongoing since 2024) illustrate how this research acceleration orientation can occur without large resources.

- **Creative Innovation Hub**

The Creative Innovation Hub module highlights more design-oriented and artistic types of engagement with cultural data, focusing more on prototyping and creative outputs. Typical activities include artistic residencies, exhibitions or art installations.

The added value of this module lies in its ability to promote more alternative perspectives on collections, going beyond traditional academic methods and perspectives. The Stabi Lab does not show a lot of examples of activities or events leaning primarily towards this orientation; one exception would be the barcamp "Die Bibliothek als Objekt (2024)", which will be discussed more in details later, where the library and its collections were interrogated and treated through the prism of artistic research methods.

- **Tech & Tools Depot**

The Tech & Tools Depot module focuses on enhancing digital literacy and providing (primarily low-threshold) access to technical infrastructure and tools. Labs in this orientation would usually provide workshops, tool demonstrations, lab sessions or consultation formats that enable users to acquire hands-on skills and to work with digital methods.

Its added value lies in lowering technical barriers and in supporting users and strengthening their skills. In the Stabi Lab, many formats represent this orientation, for example: the workshop "Text Mining mit R" (2023), the ongoing "Tool Tuesday series" or the internal "AI in Libraries" series (2025).

This module has probably the clearest correspondence to the existing typologies mentioned in Chapter 2. It resonates strongly with both Webb and Sesink's "Lab as technology depot" and Pawlicka-Deger's "work station-type lab", where the lab is primarily a place with specialised tools aiming at supporting research work. In practice however, the Stabi Lab shows that this module can often overlap with others, for example in relation with Community Building formats.

• **Tools for Reflection and Design**

To translate the framework into practice, a set of tools was developed, whose purpose is to analyse and discuss existing activities, and to inspire new ones. Those draw inspiration from Katy Kavanagh Webb's *Benchmarking Library Creative Spaces*⁷ article but have been readapted to reflect the Stabi Lab's institutional context as a state library with heterogeneous audiences and hybrid formats, in comparison to Webb's context of university libraries. Furthermore, rather than evaluating the lab as a whole, the tools operate at the granularity of events, which allow for comparison across time and formats.

- Audience

Webb's original audience tool differentiates mainly between students and researchers, which aligns well with university-based library creative spaces, which are embedded in curricula. However, for the Stabi Lab, this categorisation is insufficient and potentially even misleading, as the lab seeks to avoid reproducing hierarchical dynamics (based on academic status for example) and also explicitly addresses users who are not part of the academic world such as interested citizens, artists and library staff.

The audience tool was therefore reworked to reflect the defined target groups from the Stabi Lab concept paper. Events can be mapped to one or several audiences simultaneously, making overlaps

⁷ Webb, K. (2020). Benchmarking library creative spaces for research support and faculty/librarian partnerships. *Journal of Learning Spaces*, 9(2)

visible. This allows the tool to highlight, for example, which formats bring together different groups and which would address a narrower audience.

Other experiments with alternative dimensions (such as technical expertise versus subject knowledge) revealed some conceptual limits, due to insufficient data and also to the risk of reinforcing hierarchies of expertise. The final visualisations are included in the annex and prioritise more institutional relevance over completeness.

Figure 2: Webb's original „Audience“ tool (Webb, 2020, p. 65)

- Space/Place

The Space/Place tool was adapted to capture the hybrid character of events and differentiates between on-site, online and hybrid formats. Unlike Webb's original model, which focuses on room capacity and spatial scale (see Figure 3), this version emphasises where participation happens.

Each event is positioned on a linear axis, from online to on-site, which makes it possible to compare formats at one glance. This abstraction can be useful for identifying patterns but also highlights a limitation: hybridity encompasses different practices (for example, streaming, documentation, asynchronous reuse). Later observations showed that several types of hybridity could be distinguished but this was not implemented in the tool due to time constraints. The tool should therefore be understood as an initial mapping help.

Figure 3: Webb's original „Space Size“ tool (Webb, 2020, p. 40)

- Level of Support

The Level of Support tool was adapted from Webb's original Venn diagram, which differentiates between four modes of library support such as providing services, teaching, co-creation or communities of practice. The Venn diagram was difficult to operationalise for the analysis of the individual events. I therefore used a two-axis matrix (see Annex) to translate these categories into a model that positions events according to staff facilitation and user engagement. This simplifies more complex dynamics and cannot fully capture qualitative differences; for example, there is no graphic difference between "doing things for people" and "teaching people how". It still provides a pragmatic way to visualise patterns and possible resources positioning.

Figure 4: Level of Support (Webb, 2020, p. 66)

Applied to the Stabi Lab, these tools reveal both strengths and tensions. For instance, the Stabi Lab Forum was intended as a peer-led exchange format, but it showed an increasingly low level of participation. This kind of insights was considered into to the more structured *Datencafé* format, which combines openness with some degree of moderation and structured input sessions. These are only some short examples; they will be expanded in the next section.

These tools transform implicit practices or assumptions into explicit choices and enable reflection on the positioning of the labs. In the context of the Staatsbibliothek, and in general of other libraries or institutions, they help articulate tensions for example between openness and moderation, or between individual learning and collective practice.

These instruments are not meant to offer definitive answer but to create a shared language for thinking about what hybrid labs do and could do. In visualizing dynamics and patterns, they make the evolving identity of the lab observable and graspable, and hence more easily discussable.

3.4 The Framework as a Living Method

By combining literature review, international examples and Stabi Lab self-reflection, the framework and the tools form an iterative loop between analysis and creation. Data and observations inform the framework, which in turn, provides a lens through which practice can be assessed and refined. Ultimately, the methodology itself was meant to reflect the spirit of “labness”: situated, experimental and practice-based.

In the following chapter, this framework is applied to the Stabi Lab as a case study. It helps trace how the lab’s activities articulate with bigger institutional goals, user needs, and ideas of participation and experimentation.

4. Case Study: the Stabi Lab & its Events

The Stabi Lab was both the starting point and the testing ground for the framework developed in the previous chapter. By applying the modules and the analytical tools to the Stabi Lab, it becomes possible to see how abstract ideas translate into concrete choices. This chapter therefore focuses on the Stabi Lab as an example that makes the framework visible in practice, and at the same time helps us understand how the lab has evolved over time.

4.1 Positioning the Stabi Lab

4.1.1 Origin and Development

The Stabi Lab emerged in 2019 from the Staatsbibliothek's growing engagement with Digital Humanities. Initially founded as the SBB Lab, it was conceived primarily as a digital platform that made the datasets, interfaces and APIs of the Staatsbibliothek visible and reusable. Coordinated by a cross-departmental team, the lab functioned as a "showcase for data, demos, and experiments"⁸ aiming to lower barriers to working with cultural data and to invite users to explore these resources.

The early Stabi Lab activities were inspired by international examples, such as NYPL Labs or British Library Labs, and focused strongly on participatory formats, for example hackathons and transcription projects. In this early phase, the lab operated without a permanent physical space.

From 2024, the Stabi Lab entered a more strategic phase, where responsibility shifted to a small core team within the "User Services" department, while remaining in touch with a cross-departmental network that contributes their expertise. This phase also marked a clearer articulation of the lab's role as a hub for digital humanities and social sciences within the Staatsbibliothek. A decisive step in this development was also the opening of the Oxford Room in 2023, which provided the lab a permanent physical room and enabled a closer integration of the different dimensions of lab work.

4.1.2 Resources and Infrastructure

The Stabi Lab operates through a combination of resources, which shape its hybrid character:

- Physical space

The LabSpace is located in the Oxford Room, in the Unter den Linden building of the Staatsbibliothek. The redesign of the room by the Lab team in 2023, was a process accompanied by students from the Coburg University, as part of a cooperation seminar, and integrated lounge-like and flexible furniture, in order to make the place adaptable to various event formats (on-site and hybrid).

- Digital infrastructure

The DataLab comprises the digital offerings of Stabi Lab, which are primarily provided via the website <https://lab.sbb.berlin>. It empowers users to use the Staatsbibliothek's data-driven tools and services and provides for example descriptions and tutorials of the library's APIs. The Stabi Lab also curates and disseminates data sets that are produced during lab events (with user-generated data), projects or

⁸ Neudecker, Clemens. „SBB LAB – Schaufenster für Daten, Demos & Experimente“. (<https://blog.sbb.berlin/sbb-lab/>)

during curatorial activities by research departments. It also aims to develop experimental prototypes for data-driven work with the library's cultural data. In addition, the website serves as a central point of contact for information about DH-related events.

- Partnerships and networks

Partnerships with universities (such as the FH Potsdam), other cultural heritage institutions within the Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz and national and international lab networks inform the programming and strategic development of the Stabi Lab. These collaborations enable the lab to co-organise events and position itself within a broader ecosystem of library and GLAM labs.

Together, these resources frame the Stabi Lab as a hybrid infrastructure: a combination of space, digital infrastructure, people and networks, that support experimentation and collaborative work with cultural data. This positioning provides the foundation for the event-based practices analysed in the following sections.

4.2 Four Core Modules

The Stabi Lab's activities were analysed through the four modules introduced in Chapter 3. This allows a clearer understanding of the lab's different orientations, strengths, and gaps. Only a few examples are discussed here in detail.

4.2.1 Community Builder

The Community Builder module captures the Stabi Lab's role as a space where people meet around cultural data, exchange perspectives, and co-create meaning. It emphasises participation, storytelling, and public engagement rather than technical expertise.

Quite a few of the Stabi Lab's early and current activities are anchored in this orientation, for example the hackathons *Coding Gender* and *Coding Precarity* (2019/2020), or *culture.explore(data)* more recently in 2025. These formats are meant to attract a broader spectrum of users than research-focused events, bringing together the general public, students, creatives, or even absolute newcomers to digital methods.

Community-building activities offer low-threshold entry points. They allow participants to engage with cultural data without necessarily needing prior skills, to experiment in an informal environment, and to develop forms of collaboration. These events often mobilise users who would not necessarily attend standard workshops or academic events. Because of their wider outreach, they also help enhancing visibility for the lab and reinforcing its identity and the Staatsbibliothek's as a platform for societal discussions.

Example: the *culture.explore(data)* Hackathon (2025)

This Hackathon offers a concrete illustration of how community-oriented events work and can be analysed within the framework.

It brought together around thirty participants from heterogeneous, internationally and interdisciplinary, backgrounds with experience in the humanities and social sciences, creative industries, software development and information sciences (e.g. Art History, Design, Philosophy,

Religious Studies, History of Science, Postcolonial Studies and Conservation Science but also Data Science, Machine Learning and Web Development).

The “Community Builder” dimension of the event

- **Diverse teams, shared exploration**

Participants self-organised into (mostly) interdisciplinary groups. What mattered was not so much disciplinary identity, but the shared curiosity for a dataset and the desire to try something out together.

There were also moments where interdisciplinarity did not automatically work. One group, for instance, came from the humanities and was actively looking for someone with more technical expertise. They talked with a coder who was potentially interested, but in the end they chose not to collaborate. Although they were drawn to similar material, they did not share the same vision for what the project should become. This might be anecdotal evidence, of course, but it also reflects how disciplinary backgrounds shape expectations and workflows. Collaboration does not happen by default; it also needs alignment on a conceptual level, not only as a complementary skillset.

This dynamic fits well within the Community Builder module: collaboration grows when interests converge, not just when profiles are mixed.

- **Storytelling**

Many teams framed their projects as narratives. For example, one team decided to link two datasets containing contemporaneous cultural objects (digitized menu cards and shellac music recordings) and designed an immersive interactive web app, whose goal is for “users [to] experience what a night out in pre-First World War Berlin would have sounded and tasted like.”⁹

Another team addressed issues such as the ambiguity of historical attributions in place names through geo-visualisation but also through a playful quiz meant to “allow the audience to experience the difficulties of mapping historical geographical data”¹⁰. This suggests that community building is also tied to shared interpretation: participants form a sense of community when they jointly explore data and negotiate meaning and perspective, including the ambiguities and difficulties involved, rather than simply working alongside one another.

- **A meeting point between institutions and public**

Participants worked with datasets from different cultural institutions from Berlin and Oxford. For many, this was their first encounter with the SPK collections as datasets. The hackathon therefore acted as an interface, a moment during which the Stabi Lab and the CDS could observe how users discover, understand, or struggle with their resources and data offers.

- **Informal learning context**

Most participants had never joined a hackathon before, and some had never manipulated library datasets. Yet the informal and playful environment of the hackathon made learning possible without pressure; for example, one participant expressed the following in the feedback form following up the event: “First time I worked with data related to the cultural field, nice to see new approaches and ways data can enhance our cultural understanding.”

⁹ <https://lab.sbb.berlin/menu-music-mix/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/uncertainguineapick/uncertainties-in-the-archives>

Figure 5: Answers to the feedback form's question "6.4. I feel more confident in applying digital approaches to GLAM data following this event" (14 Responses)

What this event taught us about community building

- **Awareness and participation**

The hackathon attracted a majority of newcomers. Among the 14 feedback responses (around half of all participants), every respondent indicated that it was their first Stabi Lab event. The organizing team promoted the event across several networks and specialized communities to achieve a diverse mix of profiles. The result was indeed heterogeneous, with participants from the digital humanities, social sciences, coding bootcamps, and cultural heritage backgrounds. However, for future editions it may be beneficial to ensure a slightly higher proportion of participants with programming experience, as some teams lacked technical skills needed for certain ideas.

- **Moderation**

Although the Stabi Lab team did not want to micro-engineer the organisation of this hackathon and let flexibility and freedom to the participants, a certain amount of facilitation and guidance was necessary. This seems to indicate that community-oriented formats cannot run on openness alone and need some level of moderation or scaffolding, or practical support. The difficulty lies in that it might have to be adjusted continuously and often *ad hoc* during the event, in response to emerging needs, observed group dynamics and actual levels of experience. Some responses from the feedback form tend to address the same issues:

"As someone who had never taken part in any DH event, this was a very encouraging and welcoming space. This makes a huge difference in such a context. Also the organisers were very hands on and always had a kind word to check in and help."

"I liked the experimental nature and working in an interdisciplinary team. The organization of the hackathon, such as the process of forming groups, the structural guidelines for the two days, but still the opportunity for free and creative work, were great. The time pressure helped us not to get lost in our own topics, but to work in a focused manner within the group."

"We missed a easy option to exchange data and work collaborative, so lots of emails with code snippets were sent."

"The friendly moderation helped a lot. More time and a bit more hands-on API advice would have been useful."

- **Heterogeneity is a strength (but not automatically)**

The diversity of backgrounds created an atmosphere where expertise circulated horizontally rather than vertically. Participants learned from the available data documentation, from the experts at their disposition present on the first day but also from each other. However, it also showed some limits. A participant, for example noted: “It is a bit difficult to learn from others in this event. If you don’t get explained how topic modelling works or knowledge graph, it’s not likely you pick something up from these methods.”

Diversity increases possibility, but does not guarantee peer-learning. Interdisciplinary community-building formats might benefit from allowing more time or space for translating or building bridges between expertise domains. Otherwise, we risk “parallel voices” instead of actual exchange.

- **Community building generates new perspectives for the lab and the Staatsbibliothek**

This event helped revealing user needs (e.g. better documentation, preprocessing of some datasets) that are otherwise rarely voiced or difficult to gather. These insights are informing future work on dataset curation and event planning, for the Stabi Lab as well as for the upcoming event by the CDS in Oxford in 2026.

The projects themselves also generated new perspectives on the Staatsbibliothek collections, e.g. through cross-collection linking or through the evaluation and visualisation of the dataset of the newspaper *der Tag*, which was digitized but not yet explored within the Stabi.

The Community Builder module captures how the Stabi Lab can function as meeting point where people explore cultural data together and try out new ways of engaging with it. Through the example of the *culture.explore(data)* Hackathon, it becomes clear that such formats can reveal user needs, foster collaboration, and open the collections to new forms of engagement, which however require mindful design and facilitation to truly flourish.

4.2.2 Research Accelerator

The Research Accelerator module refers to the lab’s role as a place where researchers can experiment with data, tools, and collaborative methods. Compared to “Community Builder” formats, these activities focus more explicitly on research questions or scholarly experimentation. They attract users who would usually already have a project, a question, or simply the wish to experiment with a new method, even if they are not digital experts.

Within the Stabi Lab, this module includes formats such as *Critical Library Perspectives* (2022), the digiS Editathon to come in 2026 or the *Blauer Salon* format (that is hosted by the Stabi Lab in collaboration with the *Interdisziplinäres Zentrum Digitalität und digitale Methoden* am Campus Mitte at the Humboldt University since 2024). These events often operate at the intersection of Digital Humanities, research software engineering (RSE) and scholarly practices.

While they tend to attract smaller groups than community-driven events, “Research Accelerator” formats might be able to generate deeper and more lasting forms of engagement.

Case example: Blauer Salon

Blauer Salon is a peer-led exchange series meant to bring together researchers, data specialists and research software engineers. It offers a place for working through ideas together, not for presenting results to an audience.

Sessions usually gather between four and ten participants, often from the Staatsbibliothek and from the Humboldt University, but really open to anyone “in the field of RSE or interested in implementing specific projects”¹¹. Rather than being a workshop or a lecture format, it functions as a space for thinking together, where problems are shared and where expertise circulates horizontally.

The “Research Accelerator” dimension

- **Collaborative production of knowledge**

Participants are not meant to prepare anything but they might arrive with a piece of work, a technical question or a practical challenge they are currently having. The group collectively unpacks it and shares insight and experiences. The format supports co-reflection and co-learning and might look more like a working session or an internal lab meeting than a public event.

- **Experimental focus**

It offers a space to test ideas, present early work (e.g. one PhD student presenting the current state of their work) and get feedback before moving on to implementation or developing an idea further. The lab thus becomes a small testing ground, a place for prototyping.

- **Horizontality**

While the Stabi Lab team hosts the event physically in the Oxford room and might eventually jump in to facilitate or moderate the conversation, knowledge comes from all participants.

- **Sustained Engagement**

Blauer Salon is not meant to be a one-off event but a series which builds continuity. Returning participants can bring back updates, and the conversations then builds over time, contributing to an “accelerator” effect.

What this event teaches us about research acceleration

- **Lower public visibility but higher-research value.**

While they seem to attract and cater to fewer participants and smaller target groups than community building events, the strength of this format lies more into the “depth” that might be generated during the exchanges or across this form of engagement.

- **It generates a different understanding of user needs.**

In relation with the last point, the discussions led during *Blauer Salon* might produce interesting insights for the lab and for the lab future offerings, and reveal what more advanced users are missing, for example in terms of documentation or service offerings beyond more basic digital literacy workshops. This is especially relevant if the Stabi Lab wishes to focus more on meeting the needs of this user group.

¹¹ <https://lab.sbb.berlin/blauer-salon/>

Blauer Salon shows how the Stabi Lab can function as a Research Accelerator even without the larger technical infrastructures that some other international labs might rely on. Instead, it contributes to foster a hybrid and collaborative research culture, especially through its positioning outside of the university setting. Indeed, Blauer Salon is not structured as a seminar or a more traditionally hierarchical workshop would be and allows the participants to be less constrained by their institutional role, academic status (or lack of) as well as to be free from metrics. Through the Research Accelerator lens, Blauer Salon demonstrates how the Stabi Lab can nurture and encourage interdisciplinary exchanges and act as hub for different stakeholders.

4.2.3 Creative Innovation Hub

The goal of the Creative Innovation Hub module is to demonstrate the laboratory's function as a space where artistic practices, library collections and exploratory digital methods or prototyping come together. The activities are intended to encourage creative professionals, art students and workers, designers to interact with the Staatsbibliothek's collections outside of more traditional scholarly practices.

Within the Stabi Lab, this orientation towards this module is still quite limited and linked to a few collaborations with artistic or design schools. A recent key example would be the Barcamp "The Library as Object & the Objects of the Library", organised in partnership with the library of the Berlin University of the Arts (UdK) and NFDI4Culture.

Example: Barcamp "The Library as Object & the Objects of the Library" (2024)

Unlike a traditional conference with a programme and inputs fixed in advance, a Barcamp is an open format, whose goal is to foster exchange and participation. The participants propose directly on the day the topics they are interested to discuss and they are then accepted by the plenary and discussed in groups in parallel sessions. It is completely open-ended; it is primarily about dialogue, developing ideas and initiating contacts.

This Barcamp was primarily aimed at artists and staff of art colleges, museums and libraries, but also in general open to anyone interested in discussing cultural practices relevant to both GLAM and art institutions or creative professionals.

It was attended by around 30 people coming from museums, (art) libraries and cultural heritage and research institutions throughout Germany, and eventually addressed a broad range of curatorial issues, including the collection of zines, artistic interventions in reading rooms, enabling artistic research and rethinking the spatial organisation of library collections. It also reflected on how hybrid experimental spaces, such as the Stabi Lab, could facilitate encounters across institutional settings.

The "Creative Innovation Hub" dimension of the event

- **Libraries as spaces for artistic production**

During the Barcamp, participants explored ways in which libraries could support artistic work structurally, for instance through residencies, stipendiums or by providing a space for artistic projects. These discussions referenced existing international examples, such as the ÖNB Labs Art Programme of the Austrian National Library or the Artist Fellowship of the Bibliotheca Hertziana in Rome as points of inspiration rather than as direct outputs of the Barcamp itself. The conversations also considered the question of libraries spaces expanding to include studio or exhibition spaces, following models like the

Extended Library at the University of Fine Arts Hamburg. This reflection highlighted that even a one-time event like this one can surface ideas for future creative initiatives, helping libraries to explore and experiment with supporting artistic production in a small-scale way.

- **Transdisciplinary exchange and new partnerships (the "Hub" aspect)**

The Barcamp provided an opportunity for dialogue between art schools and institutions, libraries, and museums, which often lack structured partnerships and links. It showed that a space like the Stabi Lab can facilitate interdisciplinary discussions that do not always fit in traditional curriculum.

What this event taught us

- **Artistic perspectives can reveal blind spots in library practices**

Participants were interested in the challenges rising from collecting and cataloguing artist books, zines and other self-published or alternative artistic materials, and identified this as an aspect where libraries can innovate and adapt their services. In the case of this Barcamp, the open-ended and participatory format meant that no concrete initiatives or follow-up actions were actively generated from the event from the Staatsbibliothek itself. However, by making these challenges visible, the discussions offered an opportunity to acknowledge gaps in current services and consider how practices could be refined in the future.

- **Open-end format as a support for creative exploration**

This event was another example of the potential of an open and participatory format. A Barcamp, with its proposals and selection of topics coming from the participants themselves and with its horizontal dialogue, can be quite effective for generating ideas that would most likely not emerge in more formal and guided formats.

- **Towards StARTS libraries**

Overall, the Barcamp illustrated the Stabi Lab's potential to function as a Creative Innovation Hub, where libraries can act as incubators for artistic dialogue. As noted in „Bilder einer Buchaufstellung – Bibliotheken aus Sicht der Künste. Bericht über das Barcamp »Die Bibliothek als Objekt & die Objekte der Bibliothek«,“¹² the Barcamp highlighted the “immense opportunity that should be exploited” of engaging with artistic perspectives to rethink library practices, and eventually leading to transform state libraries into what they called StARTS libraries.

4.2.4 Tech & Tools Depot

The Tech & Tools Depot module invites us to see the lab as an access point to digital methods and tools and hands-on training. While the other modules focus on engagement or research practices, the goal here is primarily to enable and empower users to work with cultural data in a really concrete way. It could be by the means of introductory sessions, tool demonstrations, or workshops on working with the data of the Staatsbibliothek or within a broader DH context.

¹² Eichenberger, Nicole; Mathieu, Christian; Schubert, Zoe; Sternitzke, Katja. Bilder einer Buchaufstellung – Bibliotheken aus Sicht der Künste. Bericht über das Barcamp »Die Bibliothek als Objekt & die Objekte der Bibliothek«. Zeitschrift für Bibliothekswesen und Bibliographie : ZfBB. 71. 2024

Example: Tool Tuesday

An interesting example of this module is the Tool Tuesday series. The series was launched in 2023 and is currently running in its third iteration. It offers brief introductions to selected digital tools that are relevant for working with cultural heritage data. These sessions are designed to accommodate users with diverse backgrounds, but primarily aims at newcomers with little technical knowledge, as a key feature of these sessions is their no-code approach.

Tool Tuesday consists of online sessions lasting 90 minutes, requiring no prior registration, during which an established method from the Digital Humanities field is introduced. Topics include for example dataset retrieval and introductions to the APIs of cultural heritage institutions, ATR, NER, Topic Modeling. The sessions are “loosely structured as a DH ‘pipeline’”¹³, meaning starting the first of the series with data acquisition and later on going more into transformation and processing. However, they can also be attended and are meant to function individually and independently. Attendance typically ranges from 10 to 30 people.

The “Tech & Tools Depot” dimension of the event

- **Low-threshold access**

As stated, Tool Tuesday provides a practical introduction to DH topics and does not require any prior knowledge. Participants can explore a method or tool at a basic level and then decide whether or they want to pursue deeper learning by themselves. This makes the format ideal for those who are curious but would have been hesitant about joining more intensive or advanced workshops. In comparison to some other Stabi Lab’s events which require some commitment, the format might lower participation barriers, since it allows users to attend spontaneously online, without needing to register in advance and without expectation of coming back.

- **Practical orientation**

Sessions focus on concrete tasks and examples. This pragmatic focus differentiates the Tech & Tools Depot module from research-oriented formats, like *Blauer Salon*, where it is more about conceptual reflection.

- **Support for user needs**

The topics addressed in Tool Tuesday are aligned with questions or challenges that some of the lab’s users would encounter as well during other events, for example about data access and APIs. The series therefore supports Stabi Lab’s less technically-skilled users at the level where they most frequently experience difficulty.

What this series taught us

- **Heterogeneous audience and needs**

Evaluation data is still limited but it currently shows that Tool Tuesday attracts a broad mix of participants, including students, postgraduate researchers, individuals with backgrounds in History, Literature but also in Digital Humanities. Many participants identify as beginners while some others already have experience (“Advanced (some experience, but still needs to learn)”).

¹³ <https://lab.sbb.berlin/tool-tuesday/>

Participants also differ quite strongly in how the topics align with their professional or academic context: some report high relevance, others seem to join out of personal interest or curiosity. (→ “Welchen Stellenwert hat das Thema der heutigen Veranstaltung in Ihrem unmittelbaren beruflichen oder akademischen Umfeld?”)

This also poses the challenge of the design of the sessions and the pace or technical level. From some of the collected feedback, some sessions show quite a mixed range of reaction to the question “1. How would you rate the technical level of the event?”, as shown on the following figure:

1. Wie bewerten Sie das fachliche Niveau der Veranstaltung?

Antwort	Anzahl	Prozent
(1) viel zu niedrig (AO01)	0	0.00%
(2) eher zu niedrig (AO02)	1	11.11%
(3) genau richtig (AO03)	6	66.67%
(4) eher zu hoch (AO04)	2	22.22%
(5) viel zu hoch (AO05)	0	0.00%
Keine Antwort	0	0.00%

- **Insights in user needs**

Tool Tuesday can also serve as an informal platform for gathering insights into users’ needs and pain points, insights that could inform future directions for the Stabi Lab’s own documentation and online tutorials.

4.3 Applying the Tools of Chapter 3

The analytical tools that I developed in the last chapter make it possible to analyse the Stabi Lab’s activities beyond the lens of individual events. When applied to the broader Stabi Lab’s event history, dating from 2019, they can reveal patterns or gaps across audiences, hybrid practices, and the forms of support the lab provides. This section demonstrates how the tools help make these patterns visible and how they can inform the further development of the lab.

4.3.1 Audience

The Stabi Lab defines its target groups broadly: researchers and students of the humanities and social sciences with and without prior knowledge of data-driven research, creatives and cultural professionals, interested members of the public and citizen scientists and employees of the Staatsbibliothek seeking to work with digital tools or explore new approaches (e.g. AI). Because the lab is part of a research library rather than, for example, a university, it does not benefit from a “natural” or a “guaranteed” audience (like student population or professors), which makes it important to evaluate who actually participates.

Using registration data from the *culture.explore(data)* hackathon, feedback from different *Tool Tuesday* sessions and evaluation from a student workshop in collaboration with FH Potsdam, a certain picture of the Stabi Lab audience emerges.

Participation seems quite consistently the strongest among early-career or postgraduate researchers, PhD students, and humanities researchers who already have some experience or knowledge of digital tools or data.

In the hackathon registrations, for example, a large number of applicants identified their backgrounds in digital humanities. Even when applicants came from the humanities and did not have technical or computational background, many described an interest in enhancing their digital skills for ongoing or future research projects. Participants from a coding bootcamp, usually looking for hands-on experience and applied projects for their portfolio, formed the second most visible group.

However, the event was also deliberately promoted across a broad range of channels: academic mailing lists (DHD, H-Soz-Kult, diverse university departments), cultural heritage networks, NFDI partners, coding bootcamps, Berlin universities, student cafés and social media. This explains in part the strong representation of digital humanists and coders.

Undergraduate or graduate students seem to appear in the audience primarily when the lab has a direct partnership or collaboration with a university. The data from the FH Potsdam seminar but also earlier Stabi Lab's events such as *Frauen* im Fokus* or *Fanny loves Wilhelm* showed us that student engagement is most important when the event is part of the university curriculum. Outside of these partnerships, the attendance is more irregular. Tool Tuesday feedback shows for example that these sessions mostly attract staff from other (GLAM) institutions, rather than students.

This shows that the Stabi Lab successfully reaches researchers, especially early-career scholars, who are interested in digital methods and hybrid profiles, but struggles to attract a broader general public or student audience outside of structured collaborations. Some hackathon applicants also indicated a preference for remote participation, which suggests that hybrid on remote availability is a relevant aspect to take into account for audience outreach.

It also shows a gap between the Stabi Lab's goal of offering low-threshold access and the actual participation and self-selection that seems to operate. The audience composition appears to be strongly linked to the channels through which the lab decides to communicate (DH lists, GLAM networks, coding schools) and to institutional or university collaborations.

4.3.2 Space / Place / Hybridity

Mapping the Stabi Lab's activities across physical and digital environments shows that "hybridity" is not a single fixed model in the lab. Instead, it uses different configurations depending, for example, on the practical needs of the users, the level of interaction that is required or envisioned, or simply on the resources available. The analysis of on-site events in the Oxford Room (or other physical locations within the Staatsbibliothek), online formats such as *Tool Tuesday* and some hybrid sessions in series like *Blauer Salon* or in *Frauen* im Fokus* helped revealing three trends.

A first pattern concerns synchronous hybrid participation, where on-site and remote users take part in an event at the same time. Hybrid editions of the *Blauer Salon* or *Frauen* im Fokus* belong to this category. In these cases, a group of participants meets on site, while others join online simultaneously. This setup allowed participation from researchers or citizen scientists outside of Berlin or unable to attend on site on the day of the event. However, these sessions showed the limits of improvised hybrid formats: in those mentioned examples, the technical setup was often very much improvised or built on the spot, through a laptop acting as interface. Hybridity was not initially planned and conceptualized as part of the format; it surfaced because of user needs. As a result, the experience in the room differed quite a bit from the online experience and created a small friction or imbalance between the two groups.

A second pattern appears in situations where on-site activities are later extended through a digital access or replica, but without a shared live experience or interaction. This would include cases where on-site workshops or inputs are documented afterwards. While this model creates no immediate exchange between on-site and online users, it helps broadening access and helps transforming on-site activities into reusable resources. The Stabi Lab has not applied this strategy consistently, but examples such as *Faithful Transcriptions*, which had an online program of presentations, recorded and later put available on the Stabi Lab website, could lead the way for other on-site events and demonstrates that this type of practice can extend the reach of a format meaningfully.

The third and maybe most distinctive hybrid pattern in the Stabi Lab concerns formats in which the physical and the digital complement each other, instead of 'simply' duplicating. Several workshops help illustrating this approach. For example, in the seminar *Fanny loves Wilhelm*, students first got to see and interact with the original billets in the Oxford Room before moving to the transcription work based on the digitized collections. Being able to see the original letters was important for understanding the documents, while the digital versions enabled the work with transcriptions and the later processing of those.

A similar configuration appeared in the seminar on *Julie Elias*. Students engaged with physical letters and printed works from the Staatsbibliothek collections and later translated their research into two connected outputs: a physical exhibition in the Claudio-Abbado reading room and a digital exhibition on the Stabi Lab website. The physical exhibition created on-site visibility in the reading room while the digital version ensured a longer-term and remote accessibility.

The Citizen Science project *Frauen im Fokus** also followed this concept of a hybrid complementary model. Participants worked with digitised letters from the Staatsbibliothek collections but could join online or on site depending on their preference and access.

Taken together, these examples show that hybridity in the Stabi Lab is best understood as a spectrum of access modes rather than as a technical duplication of events across formats. The lab tries to function as a bridge between the physical and digital environments and collections of the Staatsbibliothek. At the same time, the cases discussed here point to aspects of the hybrid identity that could be strengthened. Much thought has gone into the spatial design of the Oxford Room to make it flexible for workshops and collaborative formats. However, less attention has so far been given to the design of the digital environment and the infrastructure needed to support remote hybrid participation more smoothly. More consistent tools for shared workspaces or synchronous interaction could help reduce the current imbalance between on-site and online users.

More broadly, the analysis seems to suggest that hybrid formats in the Stabi Lab work best when they support the lab's purpose as a connecting space, i.e. when they create meaningful connections, whether between analog collections and their digital replicas or between users on-site and online, and when they widen participation possibility and open new ways into the collections of the library.

4.3.3 Level of Support

Mapping Stabi Lab's events using the "Level of Support" model offers us an insight in how the lab positions itself in terms of facilitation and moderation: doing the work on behalf of users, working alongside them, teaching them skills or fostering communities of practice.

When looking at the Lab's activities, some clear trends emerge. Most formats oscillate between "teaching people how" and "doing with". Sessions and workshops such as *Tool Tuesday*, the *AI Series*

or one-off technical workshops are primarily oriented toward teaching and introducing tools or methods. Formats such as the hackathons, *Frauen* im Fokus* or *Fanny and Wilhelm* work more through a joint exploration, where participants also lead and moderate the sessions, contribute knowledge and shape the results. In these cases, the Stabi Lab provides some degree of facilitation and inputs, but expertise circulates more horizontally.

Attempts to build communities of practice have been and still show themselves more difficult to sustain. The *Stabi Lab Forum*, for example, was conceived as a peer-led space with almost no structure, but participation was then quite low and irregular. *Blauer Salon* has somehow a similar ambition and seems to also require some level of effort or structured invitations to maintain participation and engagement, despite benefiting from a larger community from the beginning (from the Stabi and the HU).

The Level of Support model shows us that the Lab's work focuses more in some central part of the spectrum. "Teaching how" and "doing with" formats both seem to respond well to user needs and to take into account the lab's amount of resources. At the same time, the model helps to identify where the Lab faces limitations: formats that rely on communities of practice seem to all suffer from a lack of consistent engagement and participation.

4.4 Towards Best Practices and Scalability in Chapter 5

Looking across the different modules and tools applied in this chapter, several recurring trends become visible. Taken together, they show how the Stabi Lab has developed since its creation and where challenges remain.

A first pattern concerns the audience of the Stabi Lab. Despite the stated commitment to low-threshold access, participation is shaped strongly by existing (DH) networks and collaborations. Researchers with digital interests and hybrid profiles are more consistently present, while students and a broader public of interested citizens engage mainly when the lab directly collaborates with a university. This tension appears across different formats suggests that audience diversity depends largely on targeted communication and on partnerships.

A second recurring element relates to the balance between openness and structure or moderation. Different formats, such as hackathons, barcamps, or forums, showed that horizontal exchange and openness can prove themselves really productive but also revealed that some level of support, facilitation or outreach was needed to ensure collaboration or even the perennity of a format. The "Level of Support" tool helped highlight that the Stabi Lab is usually the most effective in the middle of the spectrum, "teaching how" and "doing with", and that "communities of practice" have proven themselves to be more challenging to sustain.

The analysis also showed us that hybridity is not a single fixed model within the lab but a set of practices and modalities of access. Some hybrid setups emerged out of necessity, while others were designed from the beginning to link both physical and digital environments and act more as a bridge.

These patterns and learnings will be used in Chapter 5 to outline a set of possible best practices, to provide a foundation for thinking about how the Stabi Lab, and possibly other library labs, can support participation and develop clearer strategies for long-term engagement or hybridity practices.

5. Best Practices and Transferable Insights

The previous chapters showed that the framework developed for hybrid library labs grew out of an iterative exchange between theory, benchmarking and the practical example of the Stabi Lab. Chapter 4 then showed what happens when such a model is applied to an existing lab: it helps make implicit practices or tensions visible and highlights some possibilities that might not be obvious from the perspective of daily operations.

This chapter identifies best practices that are both grounded in the Stabi Lab case and potentially transferable to other institutions. At the same time, it outlines the limits of the framework and the conditions under which it can scale. The goal is not to prescribe a universal model for all labs, but to articulate a set of adaptable principles that can support libraries with different contexts, missions, audiences or resources.

5.1 The Framework as a Tool for Reflection

A central lesson of this project is that frameworks for library labs must remain flexible. The four modules introduced earlier offer a structured vocabulary for reflection and analysis but they are not to be taken as fixed categories. The Stabi Lab case has shown that labs operate more like constellations of practices and that these orientations can change with time depending on staff capacity, institutional priorities, partnerships or simply unexpected opportunities.

The framework should be therefore understood as a diagnostic tool, enabling labs to map what they already do, identify imbalances and decide where to reinforce some aspects or if they want experiment further in other directions.

This reflective function was central to the Stabi Lab. For example, the mapping exercise revealed that community-building and introductory formats to digital tools were strongly developed whereas artistic or creative prototyping formats were quite rare. The framework works best when used iteratively and to inform future development rather than only as an evaluation at the end of a cycle.

5.2 Defining Objectives and Making Them Visible

A recurring theme in the literature on the evaluation of library makerspaces and labs is the importance of clearly articulated objectives. In *Evaluating a Public Library Makerspace*¹⁴ for example, Pia Margaret Gahagan and Philip James Calvert show that many experimental spaces begin with an exploratory approach and avoid setting explicit goals out of fear of restricting its openness and going against the premise of it. However, this absence of objectives can lead to inconsistent practices or unclear expectations:

“Interviewees talked about starting out with an experimental approach and not wanting to be pinned down to any set objectives or outcomes. What may have been missing from these experiments was the identification of hypotheses that helped to determine whether the experiment was a success or a failure. These hypotheses would help structure the assessment while the makerspace was in its early stages and later a set of data would have been available

¹⁴ Gahagan, P. M., & Calvert, P. J. (2020). *Evaluating a Public Library Makerspace*. *Public Library Quarterly*, 39(4), 320–345. <https://doi-org-1n8f4xv6101e5.erf.sbb.spk-berlin.de/10.1080/01616846.2019.1662756>

to help inform decision making for the space upon completion of the experimental period, and to guide the creation of fresh objectives”

(Gahagan & Calvert, 2020, p. 338)

They also highlight that having clearly defined objectives is important for choosing appropriate evaluation methods. In the Stabi Lab, objectives are formulated, but often not translated into more concrete or measurable targets. This means that quantitative indicators such as attendance numbers or website statistics can only play a limited role. They help us understand reach but might not capture the more relevant and interesting outcomes of the lab’s work and missions, for example fostering (interdisciplinary) exchange, engagement with the collections or users expanding their technical skills or understanding of cultural data.

These aspects are indeed more visible through qualitative assessment such as observations made during events. This type of insight can be more meaningful than purely quantitative metrics, and can be easily integrated into the lab’s evaluation routine.

5.3 Evaluation and Ongoing Practice

Building on these insights, ongoing evaluation can inform labs as to whether they are meeting their objectives and help them to adjust their practices accordingly. Gahagan and Calvert highlight that evaluation should not be considered a summative reporting activity but more seen as a continuous practice that informs design. This also aligns with the ethos of experimentation, iteration and self-reflection found in digital humanities labs and makerspace culture.

For the Stabi Lab, integrating evaluation into the workflow, even in a simple form, proved extremely valuable. Short feedback forms, reflection sessions at the end of events and informal conversations provided insights in improving the events and identifying user needs. Other labs can adopt this by incorporating small evaluation moments throughout their activities. They do not require sophisticated tools but might prove more useful when they are consistent enough to capture patterns and transformations over time. When combined with the four modules or the analytical tools of Chapter 3, these insights can help guide strategic decisions without requiring a lot of resources.

5.4 Hybridity

Chapter 4 demonstrated that hybridity in the Stabi Lab is not simply about streaming or duplicating events. Hybrid practices were most effective when they reinforced the Lab’s identity and mission as a connecting space, between different communities and disciplines, between on-site and remote users, or as a bridge between analogue and digital collections. On the other hand, hybrid formats were weaker when they were improvised or lacked the necessary tools and infrastructure for remote collaboration.

The transferable insight is that hybridity should be guided by function rather than technology, as a way to extend reach and support reusability. This approach does not necessarily require complex infrastructure. Even more modest practices like documenting on-site events or organizing small but well-planned hybrid events and discussions, as a way to break potential accessibility problems, can have a meaningful impact.

Documentation might provide a particularly interesting example as a scalable hybrid tool. By recording presentations, publishing tutorials or datasets or creating small digital exhibitions, the Stabi Lab for

example transformed single events into reusable and online resources. Through such practices, labs can expand their outreach without needing to host even more events and a lot more resources, making hybridity a strategic tool for smaller labs as well.

5.5 Balancing Openness and Structure

The Stabi Lab demonstrated a recurring tension between openness and structure across its different formats. While hackathons, barcamps and peer-exchange formats thrive on openness, they also require some level of facilitation to ensure participation and equality of exchange. In contrast, other formats such as Tool Tuesday or technical workshops rely more on structure and predefined learning goals but they can also benefit from moments of flexibility based on the needs of the participants.

The Level of Support tool introduced in Chapter 3 helped visualise this balance. Most Stabi Lab formats fall somewhere in the middle of the spectrum: teaching people how, and doing things? with. Peer-led formats and communities of practice proved much harder to sustain without extra coordination from the Stabi Lab staff. This insight can help other labs to anticipate where they might need to allocate staff time and resources, determine where more structured support may be required to encourage and sustain participation and whether it might be overly ambitious or not to design formats based on community of practice, if there is not an already existing and mostly self-organized group.

Some events such as the *culture.explore(data)* Hackathon showed us that it is essential to strike a good balance between openness and structure. Although labs often rely on creativity and some level of freedom and agency, it also needs organisational support to work well, e.g. providing clear expectations (for example indicating the expertise level of an event, whether to bring a laptop, etc.), an indicative schedule or preparing in advance some basic collaborative digital tools (pads, folders) can help participants to orient themselves and engage more fully in the event.

5.6 Participation and Partnerships

A third major insight concerns the audience. Even though the Stabi Lab offers low-threshold access and open formats, participation in events usually reflect more its own links to other institutions, networks or used channels of communication. Broader public audiences or undergraduate students participated mainly when the event was embedded in a partnership with a university seminar or was part of a citizen-science initiative.

This suggested that audience diversity depends strongly on partnerships rather than on the openness of the format alone. For other labs, this means that strategic links to universities, community groups or other cultural institutions are essential for diversifying participation and also valuable for creating more predictable and sustained forms of engagement. In terms of scalability, it means that even smaller labs can do this by forming one or a few partnerships with local groups or organisations.

The Stabi Lab's case, especially through the example of the recent *culture.explore(data)* Hackathon, also shows the importance of communicating through diverse channels. A transferable best practice would be to map communication channels to intended user groups and to review and evaluate the efficiency of this mapping.

5.7 Navigating Ambiguity

A central and recurring insight across the Stabi Lab case and literature review is that hybrid library labs operate in certain conditions of ambiguity and therefore reveal tensions. Indeed, labs often sit between categories: between service and research, between experimentation and flexibility and institutional momentum, between physical and digital spaces.

Rather than treating this ambiguity as a problem, a source of frustration or a sign of conceptual vagueness, it can be understood as generative for insights. Ambiguity creates room for exploration, for unexpected connections between communities. This is also why the four modules introduced in this framework inevitably overlap in practice. Some events aim at community-building, while introducing tools, fostering research exchange, and encourage creative prototyping at the same time; for example, a citizen-science event where participants would use *eScriptorium* and later be encouraged to write scientific articles using their earlier transcription work and digital methods and tools. In this example, some participants could approach the transcription work as a mainly technical learning task, focusing on learning more about the tool, whereas others could see the same activity more as a way to engage with historical material and to engage in a more epistemic approach. Instead of considering this an ambiguity about the nature of the task, it can create discussion about neutrality or materiality and it can become generative of new insights for future workshops.

Acknowledging these overlaps prevents the framework from becoming prescriptive and keeps it open enough to reflect the complexity of lab practices. Based on this observation and the other insights discussed in this chapter, two overarching best practices emerge: intentionality, for articulating objectives clearly enough and therefore consciously guiding design choices, evaluation, partnerships, and flexibility to be able to allow these objectives to evolve as user needs surface or as priorities and strategies shift. Taken together, these principles can help labs navigate their inherent complexity and hybrid nature without losing direction; rather than trying to evacuate it, labs can productively use and navigate the inherent ambiguities.

This chapter has articulated a set of best practices derived from the Stabi Lab case and tested through the proposed framework. Rather than offering a prescriptive model, the framework is intended as a tool for structured reflection that can be adapted to different institutional contexts, resources and missions.

At the same time, its applicability depends on a certain degree of organisational flexibility and openness to experimentation, which may not be equally present in all library environments. Future use in other lab contexts could help us understand better where the framework is informative and where its scope is limited and help us provide a more nuanced and maybe more complete understanding of those best practices.

Overall, the framework offers a method for labs to engage in structured reflection and experimentation and aims to offer a vocabulary to accompany iterative learning, while remaining sensitive to different context and resources.

6. Conclusion

Through this study, I aimed at exploring how hybrid cultural data labs in library context could be understood and analysed. In the context of the BKM-funded project *“Die Staatsbibliothek als Mitmach-Raum”*, the research combined perspectives on labs from digital humanities and library and information science with an analysis of pilot formats or recent events from the Stabi Lab. By doing so, I tried to develop a framework able to describe existing practices, articulate tensions, gaps or implicit assumptions and reflect on those, and would therefore help informing future strategic decisions, for the Stabi Lab as well as for other similar institutions.

6.1 Findings

A first major finding concerns the role of practice and iteration. Since its creation in 2019, the Stabi Lab evolved mostly through experimentation, through opportunities for collaboration or testing new formats for example, rather than by following a fixed strategic program. Many insights presented in this study emerged from moments of friction or from formats that were not quite successful on all aspects, but therefore could inform us on some shortcomings or blind spots of the lab’s offers and current state. This highlights and exemplifies the nature of labs as places of experimentation and open-ended and reflective practices.

Hybridity was another key aspect of this study. Through the review of scholarly discourses and through the examination of the Stabi Lab, emerged a concept of hybridity that was not entirely defined or clear at the beginning. Indeed, in the Stabi Lab case, as in other similar institutions, hybridity is not limited to the coexistence of analogue and digital environments, or to the mere translation of one to another; it shapes the formats, the interactions with the collections and between participants and therefore the production of knowledge itself.

Throughout the project, it also became increasingly clear that acknowledging the inherent tensions in library or digital humanities labs is important: the Stabi Lab has to negotiate its identity and priorities between open and low-threshold offerings and more advanced digital scholarship formats, or between its experimentative and exploratory nature and the institutional momentum of the Staatsbibliothek for example. One key insight was to approach these tensions as productive and generative of new understanding, especially when shaping or reflecting on formats, rather than as sources of frustration or ambiguity to be eliminated or to be solved.

These findings and insights are mirrored in the modular structure of the framework developed during this research. While it initially started as a typology, this modular nature quickly emerged as a way to allow different orientations to coexist and offer a vocabulary that can be easily transferable to other institutions, instead of forcing labs into a fixed or singular identity.

6.2 Limitations and Future Perspectives

This research is largely based on a single, extensive study of the Stabi Lab, which might limit its comparative scope. Future research could apply the framework developed here to other library labs, especially academic labs outside of a university context, to test its adaptability and refine it further.

Another limitation of this study lies in its relatively restricted and selective review of the existing literature on library or GLAM labs. Indeed, I deliberately focused on a small number of conceptual foundations, namely the work of Pawlicka-Deger and Webb and Sesink, in order to ground the

framework later developed in Chapter 3. While other perspectives and publications informed the research, they were not integrated into the body of analysis itself due to limitations of space as well as concerns of coherence and analytical depth.

The case study of the Stabi Lab also presented some limitations, especially with regard to the empirical material or data supporting these analysis and findings. Some formats and events, such as the *culture.explore(data)* hackathon, generated quite a rich documentation and extensive participant feedback, while others produced little to no comparable material. At times, the analysis might have therefore extrapolated from limited data. However, rather than treating this as a failure, these gaps can invite us to reflect on pain points and to consider future strategies and formats for gathering observations, event documentation or participant feedback.

6.3 Final Remarks

Throughout this project, I approached the Stabi Lab as a case study for hybrid cultural data labs and as invitation to reflect on practices, communities' ties, relationships and expectations.

A key aspect of this research is that such labs cannot be understood meaningfully through the lens of a single function or mission and must allow for the coexistence of different orientations, such as research support, public engagement or the mediation of digital tools and methods., which might overlap or pull in different directions This may be one of the defining features of most current library labs, particularly in institutions similar to the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, without a clearly delimited user group. This framework aimed at making this plurality, and sometimes ambiguity, visible and explicit, without creating a hierarchy or a linear structure.

Hybrid library labs open up new possibilities, beyond traditional library services but also require a certain tolerance for uncertainty, exploratory processes and thus ongoing adjustments. Instead of attempting to resolve these tensions, the study argues for acknowledging them as constitutive of the lab's nature and work. Seen in this way, hybrid labs represent one possible response to the broader transformations and challenges that are currently arising in libraries. The framework that was developed and proposed for this project is therefore not intended as a final assessment tool, but as a reflective support to accompany experimentation and learning, both within the Stabi Lab and in the wider landscape of GLAM and library labs.

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Appendices

Event Name;Start date;End date;Community Builder;Research Accelerator;Creative Innovation Hub;Tech & Tools Depot;Lab_Involvement;User_Engagement;Space;Audience
Blauer Salon;2024;2025;low;high;low;low;low;high;onsite;Researchers,Students
DatenCafe;2025;2025;medium;low;medium;medium;medium;low;onsite;Public,Researchers,Students,Internal
CultureExploreData Hackathon;2025;2025;high;low;medium;low;medium;high;onsite;Researchers,Public,Creatives,Students

Appendix 1: Snippet of the CSV document used for the tools

```

import marimo

__generated_with = "0.19.4"
app = marimo.App()

@app.cell
def _(mo):
    mo.md(
        """
        # Audience Visualization Tools
        """
    )
    return

@app.cell
def _():
    import pandas as pd
    import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
    import marimo as mo

    df = pd.read_csv("events.csv", sep=";")
    return df, mo, plt

@app.cell
def _(df, mo):
    audience_map = {
        "Internal": 0.1,
        "Researchers": 0.3,
        "Students": 0.5,
        "Public": 0.7,
        "Creatives": 0.9,
    }

    years = sorted(df["Start date"].unique())
    events = sorted(df["Event Name"].unique())

    multiselect_years = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Year(s)", options=years)
    multiselect_events = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Event(s)", options=events)

    mo.hstack([multiselect_years, multiselect_events])
    return audience_map, multiselect_events, multiselect_years

@app.cell
def _(df, multiselect_events, multiselect_years):
    filtered = df[
        df["Start date"].isin(multiselect_years.value)
        & df["Event Name"].isin(multiselect_events.value)
    ]
    return (filtered,)

@app.cell
def bubble_overlap_plot(audience_map, filtered, plt):
    from collections import defaultdict
    import numpy as np

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 4))
    positions = defaultdict(list)
    for i, (_, row) in enumerate(filtered.iterrows()):
        audiences = [a.strip() for a in row["Audience"].split(",")]
        num_aud = len(audiences)
        x = np.mean([audience_map.get(aud, 0.5) for aud in audiences])
        y = i * 0.1
        ax.scatter(x, y, s=num_aud * 150, color="blue", alpha=0.6, edgecolor="black")
        ax.text(x, y + 0.02, row["Event Name"], ha="center", fontsize=8)
        for aud in audiences:
            ax.plot(
                [x, audience_map.get(aud, 0.5)],
                [y, y],
                color="gray",
                alpha=0.4,
                linestyle="--",
            )

    ax.set_xlim(0, 1)
    ax.set_xticks(list(audience_map.values()))
    ax.set_xticklabels(list(audience_map.keys()))
    ax.set_yticks([])
    ax.set_title("Bubble Tool")
    ax.grid(axis="x", linestyle="--", alpha=0.3)
    plt.gca()
    return (np,)

@app.cell
def _(audience_map, filtered, np, plt):
    import matplotlib.cm as cm

    def event_constellation_by_event(filtered_df, audience_map_local):
        fig_ev, ax_ev = plt.subplots(figsize=(8, 8))
        center_x_ev, center_y_ev = 0.5, 0.5
        angle_step_ev = 360 / len(audience_map_local)
        aud_pos_ev = {}

        for idx_aud_ev, aud_cat_ev in enumerate(audience_map_local.keys()):
            angle_ev = np.deg2rad(idx_aud_ev * angle_step_ev)
            aud_pos_ev[aud_cat_ev] = (
                center_x_ev + 0.4 * np.cos(angle_ev),
                center_y_ev + 0.4 * np.sin(angle_ev),
            )


```

<pre> ax_ev.scatter(*aud_pos_ev[aud_cat_ev], s=200, color="lightgray", label="_nolegend_") ax_ev.text(aud_pos_ev[aud_cat_ev][0], aud_pos_ev[aud_cat_ev][1] + 0.02, aud_cat_ev, ha="center",) num_events = len(filtered_df) colors_ev = cm.get_cmap("tab20", num_events) for idx_ev, (_, event_row_ev) in enumerate(filtered_df.iterrows()): jitter_x_ev = center_x_ev + np.random.uniform(- 0.02, 0.02) jitter_y_ev = center_y_ev + np.random.uniform(- 0.02, 0.02) color_ev = colors_ev[idx_ev] event_name_ev = event_row_ev["Event Name"] event_audiences_ev = [a.strip() for a in event_row_ev["Audience"].split(",")] for aud_cat_ev in event_audiences_ev: x_aud_ev, y_aud_ev = aud_pos_ev[aud_cat_ev] ax_ev.plot([jitter_x_ev, x_aud_ev], [jitter_y_ev, y_aud_ev], color=color_ev, alpha=0.6,) ax_ev.scatter(jitter_x_ev, jitter_y_ev, s=50, color=color_ev, alpha=0.7, label=event_name_ev,) </pre>	<pre> handles_ev, labels_ev = ax_ev.get_legend_handles_labels() by_label_ev = dict(zip(labels_ev, handles_ev)) ax_ev.legend(by_label_ev.values(), by_label_ev.keys(), title="Events", loc="right", bbox_to_anchor=(1.15, 0.5),) ax_ev.set_xlim(0, 1) ax_ev.set_ylim(0, 1) ax_ev.axis("off") ax_ev.set_title("Event Constellation") return fig_ev fig_events = event_constellation_by_event(filtered, audience_map) plt.gca() return if __name__ == "__main__": app.run() </pre>
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Appendix 2: Marimo Notebook Code for the Audience Tool

Event Constellation

Appendix 3: Graphic Visualisation of the Audience Tool / Event Constellation

Bubble Tool

Appendix 4: Graphic Visualisation of the Audience Tool / Bubble Chart

<pre> import marimo __generated_with = "0.19.4" app = marimo.App() @app.cell def _(mo): mo.md(""" # Space/Place tool """) return @app.cell def _(): import marimo as mo import pandas as pd import numpy as np import matplotlib.pyplot as plt df = pd.read_csv('events.csv', sep=';') df.columns = [col.strip(';') for col in df.columns] return df, mo, plt @app.cell def _(df, mo): format_map = {"online": 0.1, "hybrid": 0.5, "onsite": 0.9} years = sorted(df['Start date'].unique()) events = sorted(df['Event Name'].unique()) multiselect_years = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Year(s)", options=years) multiselect_events = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Event(s)", options=events) mo.hstack([multiselect_years, multiselect_events]) return format_map, multiselect_events, multiselect_years @app.cell def _(df, multiselect_events, multiselect_years): filtered_df = df[df['Start date'].isin(multiselect_years.value) & df['Event Name'].isin(multiselect_events.value)] return (filtered_df, </pre>	<pre> @app.cell def _(filtered_df, format_map, plt): fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 2)) ax.set_xlim(0, 1) ax.set_ylim(-0.2, 0.3) ax.axhline(0, color='black', linewidth=0.5) y_base = 0.05 y_offsets = [i * 0.03 for i in range(len(filtered_df))] for i, (_, row) in enumerate(filtered_df.iterrows()): x = format_map.get(str(row["Space"]).lower(), 0.5) y = y_base + y_offsets[i] ax.plot(x, y, 'o', color='blue') ax.text(x, y + 0.01, row["Event Name"], ha='center', fontsize=9) ax.set_xticks([0, 0.5, 1]) ax.set_xticklabels(['Online', 'Hybrid', 'On Site']) ax.set_yticks([]) ax.grid(axis='x', linestyle='--', alpha=0.3) ax.set_title("Formats across Space/Place", fontsize=11) return if __name__ == "__main__": app.run() if __name__ == "__main__": app.run() </pre>
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Appendix 5: Marimo Notebook Code for the Space/Place Tool

Appendix 6: Graphic Visualisation of the Space/Place Tool

<pre> import marimo __generated_with = "0.19.4" app = marimo.App() @app.cell def _(mo): mo.md(""" # 4 Core Modules """) return @app.cell def _(): import marimo as mo import pandas as pd import numpy as np import matplotlib.pyplot as plt df = pd.read_csv('events.csv', sep=';') df.columns = [col.strip(';') for col in df.columns] df return df, mo, np, plt @app.cell def _(): # mo.ui.data_explorer(df) return @app.cell def _(df, mo): categories = ['Community Builder', 'Research Accelerator', 'Creative Innovation Hub', 'Tech & Tools Depot'] value_map = {'low': 1, 'medium': 5, 'high': 10} years = sorted(df['Start date'].unique()) events = sorted(df['Event Name'].unique()) multiselect_years = mo.ui.multiselect(options=years) multiselect_events = mo.ui.multiselect(options=events) mo.hstack([multiselect_years, multiselect_events]) </pre>	<pre> return categories, multiselect_events, multiselect_years, value_map @app.cell def _(df, multiselect_events, multiselect_years): filtered_df = df[df['Start date'].isin(multiselect_years.value) & df['Event Name'].isin(multiselect_events.value)] filtered_df return (filtered_df,) @app.cell def _(categories, filtered_df, np, plt, value_map): def create_radar_chart(data, categories, value_map): n = len(categories) angles = np.linspace(0, 2 * np.pi, n, endpoint=False).tolist() angles += angles[:1] fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(7, 7), subplot_kw={'projection': 'polar'}) for _, row in data.iterrows(): values = [value_map.get(str(row[cat])).lower(), 0] for cat in categories] values += values[:1] ax.fill(angles, values, alpha=0.2) ax.plot(angles, values, linewidth=2, label=row["Event Name"]) ax.set_xticks(angles[:-1]) ax.set_xticklabels(categories) ax.set_yticklabels([]) ax.legend(loc='upper right', bbox_to_anchor=(1.3, 1.1)) return ax create_radar_chart(filtered_df, categories, value_map) return if __name__ == "__main__": app.run() </pre>
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Appendix 7: Marimo Notebook Code for the Four Code Modules Visualisation

Appendix 8: Graphic Visualisation of the Four Core Modules

<pre> import marimo __generated_with = "0.19.4" app = marimo.App() @app.cell def _(mo): mo.md(""" # Level of Support Tool **Lab involvement (staff facilitation)** High: active facilitation / moderation, teaching or doing things for participants (no graphic differentiation) Medium: co-working Low: staff present but minimal guidance **User engagement / production** High: participants co-create or produce outputs themselves Medium: participants partially contribute Low: participants mostly observe / receive knowledge """) return @app.cell def _(): import pandas as pd import matplotlib.pyplot as plt import marimo as mo df = pd.read_csv("events.csv", sep=";") return df, mo, plt @app.cell def _(df, mo): # Map categorical levels to numeric positions for plotting involvement_map = {"low": 0.1, "medium": 0.5, "high": 0.9} engagement_map = {"low": 0.1, "medium": 0.5, "high": 0.9} years = sorted(df["Start date"].unique()) events = sorted(df["Event Name"].unique()) multiselect_years = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Year(s)", options=years) multiselect_events = mo.ui.multiselect(label="Select Event(s)", options=events) mo.hstack([multiselect_years, multiselect_events]) return (engagement_map, involvement_map, multiselect_events, multiselect_years,) </pre>	<pre> @app.cell def _(df, multiselect_events, multiselect_years): filtered = df[df["Start date"].isin(multiselect_years.value) & df["Event Name"].isin(multiselect_events.value)] filtered return (filtered,) @app.cell def _(engagement_map, filtered, involvement_map, plt): from collections import defaultdict import numpy as np fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(6, 6)) positions = defaultdict(list) for _, row in filtered.iterrows(): x = engagement_map.get(row["User_Engagement"].lower(), 0.5) y = involvement_map.get(row["Lab_Involvement"].lower(), 0.5) # Stack overlapping events vertically offset = 0.03 * len(positions[(x, y)]) positions[(x, y)].append(row["Event Name"]) ax.scatter(x, y + offset, color="darkgreen") ax.text(x, y + offset + 0.02, row["Event Name"], ha="center", fontsize=8) ax.set_xlim(0, 1) ax.set_ylim(0, 1) ax.set_xticks([0.1, 0.5, 0.9]) ax.set_xticklabels(["Low User Engagement", "Medium", "High User Engagement"]) ax.set_yticks([0.1, 0.5, 0.9]) ax.set_yticklabels(["Low Staff Involvement", "Medium", "High Staff Involvement"]) ax.set_title("Level of Support: User Engagement x Staff Involvement") ax.grid(alpha=0.3) plt.gca() return if __name__ == "__main__": app.run() </pre>
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Appendix 9: Marimo Notebook Code for the Level of Support Tool

Appendix 10: Graphic Visualisation of the Level of Support Tool